

IAU100 Celebrations Launched at the IAU General Assembly in Vienna

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The International Astronomical Union (IAU) is eager to celebrate its 100th anniversary in 2019. Celebrations and events will take place year-round to stimulate worldwide interest in astronomy and science.

As part of the central theme Under One Sky, the IAU will reflect upon important milestones and discoveries in the past century, while looking ahead at what is to come. Events and activities will be open to all ages and will take place at a regional, national and international level. The IAU invites the global astronomical community, policy makers, students and the general public to take part in the IAU100 celebrations.

IAU100 Global Projects Overview

The IAU is organising a comprehensive programme of flagship initiatives to reach target audiences worldwide through the IAU National Outreach Coordinators and national astronomical societies. Below is an overview of just some of the exciting events planned for IAU100.

Above and Beyond Exhibition

The Above and Beyond open source exhibition was launched at the 2018 IAU General Assembly in Vienna, Austria. The exhibition was commissioned as part of the IAU 100th anniversary celebrations and showcases some of the most significant and surprising astronomical breakthroughs that have shaped science, technology and culture over the last century. Designed in the spirit of open science, it is designed as a travelling exhibition, touring major European cities in 2018 and 2019, and is accompanied by an open source toolkit to develop a variety of exhibition experiences worldwide. The exhibition is a collaboration between the International Astronomical Union and Science Now, a science communication and strategic design studio.¹

100 Hours of Astronomy

This project invites anyone to arrange stargazing and other astronomy-related events around the world from 10 to 13 January 2019 to kick-off the anniversary celebrations. Organisers get a chance to win exciting prizes.²

IAU Einstein Schools

This initiative will develop a global network of Einstein schools with classes and clubs for learning about gravitation and general relativity and their relevance to the 1919 solar eclipse, which will have its 100th anniversary in 2019.³

Dark Skies for All

This effort will raise awareness about the preservation of quiet and dark skies. The project will encourage individuals to organise activities worldwide around the UNESCO International Day of Light, which is on 16 May. A call for Dark Skies ambassadors will be launched in autumn 2018.⁴

50th Anniversary of Moon Landing — Let's Observe the Moon!

IAU will encourage people worldwide to celebrate the 50th anniversary of the landing on the Moon on 20 July 2019 by organising activities related to space and Moon observations.⁵

Name ExoWorlds II

This initiative provides an opportunity for all the countries of the world to name an exoplanetary system.⁶

Inspiring Stars

This international exhibition highlights global initiatives that address the concept of inclusion in astronomy outreach and careers. The exhibition premiered in Vienna in August 2018 during the IAU General Assembly and will be organised in different countries throughout 2019.⁷

Open Astronomy Schools

This project will build teachers' knowledge on scientific topics and teaching techniques by organising teacher training worldwide to enable the development

of scientific literacy and the acquisition of 21st century skills.⁸

IAU Women and Girls in Astronomy Day

This project will celebrate the United Nations International Day of Women and Girls in Science on 11 February through the organisation of activities involving astronomy.⁹

Get involved!

We have launched a new website dedicated to the IAU100 celebrations which talks about the multitude of astronomy events taking place worldwide and offers further information about the programmes and partnership opportunities.

Whether you are a professional working in astronomy, an amateur astronomer or

just someone interested in astronomy, we would love for you to get involved in the celebrations. Please check IAU100 for the latest updates and get in touch with the IAU100 Secretariat for sponsorship opportunities or to endorse your astronomy event and have it included in the IAU100 Event Programme.

Full IAU100 website: www.iau-100.org

Notes

- ¹ Exhibition website: <http://100exhibit.iau.org/>
- ² 100 Hours of Astronomy website: www.100hoursofastronomy.org
- ³ Einstein schools website www.einsteinschools.org/
- ⁴ Dark skies for all website: www.iau-100.org/dark-skies-for-all
- ⁵ Moon landing anniversary website: www.iau-100.org/moon-landing-anniversary

- ⁶ Name ExoWorlds II website: www.iau-100.org/name-exoworlds
- ⁷ Inspiring stars website: www.iau-100.org/inspiring-stars
- ⁸ Open Astronomy Schools website: www.iau-100.org/open-astronomy-schools
- ⁹ Women and girls day website: www.iau-100.org/women-girls-astronomy-day

Biographies

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Call for IAU National Outreach Coordinators (NOCs)

Dear colleagues,

The IAU is seeking candidates to become the National Outreach Coordinators (NOCs), the NOCs will play a significant role in coordinating the IAU 100th anniversary activities. If your country/region does not have a NOC, and if you are interested, please contact outreach@iau.org or forward this message to any potential candidates.

The current list of NOCs is on <https://www.iau.org/public/noc/>
Further details on NOCs is available on <https://www.iau.org/public/noc/role/>

IAU Office for Astronomy Outreach